

INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN TEACHING VOCABULARY IN FOREIGN LANGUAGES

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Abstract. *There is a large collection of teaching materials for people with different levels of language skills. Success in achieving this goal depends on the practical skills and qualifications of the teachers. The ability to use information technology and modern teaching methods helps to quickly grasp new materials.*

Keywords: *innovative technologies, teaching vocabulary, methods, skills of teachers.*

ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ТЕХНОЛОГИИ В ОБУЧЕНИИ ЛЕКСИКЕ НА ИНОСТРАННЫХ ЯЗЫКАХ

Аннотация. *Существует большая коллекция учебных материалов для людей с разным уровнем владения языком. Успех в достижении этой цели зависит от практических навыков и квалификации преподавателей. Умение использовать информационные технологии и современные методы обучения помогает быстро усваивать новые материалы.*

Ключевые слова: *инновационные технологии, преподавание лексики, методы, мастерство преподавателей.*

Today, foreign language skills are becoming an integral part of vocational education. Due to the high level of cooperation with foreign partners in various fields, the demand for language learning is high. In modern society, foreign languages are becoming an important part of vocational education. Such knowledge is first acquired by people in schools, colleges, lyceums, and later in institutes, training courses, or by familiarizing themselves with basic information sets that help them learn a foreign language independently. There is a large collection of teaching materials for people with different levels of language skills. Success in achieving this goal depends on the practical skills and qualifications of the teachers. The ability to use information technology and modern teaching methods helps to quickly grasp new materials.¹ By combining different methods, a teacher is able to solve specific curricula. In this regard, teachers and students need to become familiar with modern methods of teaching foreign languages. As a result, they develop the skills to choose the most effective ways to achieve their goals. Using a variety of teaching and learning methods can be effective. Teaching takes place in small steps and is based on the student's existing knowledge system.² As time goes on, innovation in every field increases. There are also different styles of language teaching. In English language teaching, step-by-step teaching, depending on the learner's potential and level of age, gives good results. Students are divided into groups based on elementary education, intermediate education, and advanced education. A special program will be developed by the teacher for each stage.

At the initial stage, the emphasis is on pronunciation. According to Harmer, the first requirement of a native speaker is pronunciation. At the beginning of the learning process, the teacher should focus on the student's pronunciation. Although grammar and vocabulary are important, it is useless if the speaker mispronounces them. Native speakers can also understand speech with grammatical errors if the speaker pronounces the words correctly.³ Therefore, in

teaching, the main focus is on pronunciation. In this case, the use of different audios of native speakers gives good results. The teacher should teach the correct pronunciation of letters and words during the lesson. There is also a strong emphasis on oral and reading skills in the early stages. If we look at the types of speech activities of foreign language teaching, it is necessary to perform the following tasks in their teaching:

- a) Create a reading mechanism;
- b) Improving oral reading techniques;
- c) Teach them to understand what they are reading.

At the elementary level, there is a strong emphasis on reading aloud. Reading texts are also becoming simpler and more complex. However, it should be noted that although the work in the early stages is mainly focused on the development of oral skills, it does not solve the problem of developing oral speech in English. He is only in the process of preparing to work on a real speech. In addition, reading words beautifully and fluently increases a student's love of learning the language.

In addition, students will be introduced to The Present Indefinite Tense, The Past Indefinite Tense., are required to be familiar with verb tenses such as The Future Indefinite Tense and to be able to use verb forms vividly in these tenses. Students will learn the use of nouns in the singular and plural, the addition of the suffix "s" or "es" to the third person singular form of the verb in the present indefinite tense, and the interrogative, negative, and imperative forms of sentences. during the study period.

At the intermediate stage of teaching English, the focus should be on using techniques that help to increase thinking, speaking, and initiative in reading and understanding larger texts. Students will be given homework assignments. Exercises to check comprehension of the text are given and can be expressed as follows:

Answer the question on the text Samarkand: Why Samarkand is called like this? Where is the ancient center of the city? How many population is there?

Question-answer exercises are used to strengthen the student's speech, improve memory, and repeat. New words from the text are memorized. Questioning and answering will help you to memorize the words and use them in your speech. In addition, a variety of games in the classroom will increase the student's interest in learning the language and speed up the learning process. In the Hot Ball game, students form a circle and say one of the new words to the ball. Participants do not repeat each other's words, are expelled from the game if they repeat or stop speaking. That's the way to play.

In the middle stage, grammar is taught in more depth than in the first stage, and students are given exercises, tests and tests based on the rules of grammar.

Computer and phone language learning programs are also great for elementary and middle school language learning. Examples include Talk (English speaking practice), Daily English, Learn English (English master), How to speak real English. These programs are designed to include reading, listening, and test sections. Recording new words on a phone Dictaphone in your spare time is another great way to repeat. Also, showing more English subtitles and cartoons is an effective way to teach the language. At the advanced level, independent work plays a special role, especially in a foreign language. The course requirements at this stage are different from those at the previous stages. The lesson is no longer based on oral speech, because at this stage most of the

language material is studied passively (receptively). That is, reading comprehension plays a key role.4 Texts are also large in size and language material is complex. Reading, speaking, listening exercises are held regularly. When organizing a lesson, a separate day is set for Reading, a separate day for Speaking, and a separate day for Listening. Homework is also more complex than previous steps. Speaking lessons include a 2-minute talk with a topic. Alternatively, text cards will be distributed to students. Each student gives their opinion on the topic on the card of their choice. The speech requires the use of previously used phrases, phrases, introductory words, new words, synonyms.

Homework can be used to prepare additional text topics using the press, periodicals, media, and online materials. Students will be interested to learn about interesting research and scientific discoveries. In conclusion, modern language teaching is aimed at forming a more cultured individual who has the skills to self-analyze and systematize new knowledge.

Innovative methods are an integral part of modernizing the entire system. With this in mind, teachers can become acquainted with the most advanced approaches and then combine them and use them in their work to achieve significant growth in the education system. Many organizations are moving to a new level, using multimedia capabilities to send and receive information. The use of computers and other devices determines the success of the whole educational process.

Adequate attention should be paid to the formation of speech skills and the development of social resilience in educational training. In addition, the success of any lesson in education depends in many ways on the proper organization of lessons. The lesson should be based on the creative collaboration of teacher and student. Only then will students be able to think independently and develop their abilities.

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